
iAtlantic Deliverable D7.2

GEOSS Atlantic Ocean Observation Community Mirror Site

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Table of Contents

LIST OF FIGURES	3
1. SUMMARY	4
2. MOTIVATION FOR AN ALL ATLANTIC COMMUNITY DATA PORTAL	4
3. GEOSS – THE GLOBAL EARTH OBSERVATION SYSTEM OF SYSTEMS	5
3.2. GEOSS – DATA AND RESOURCES	6
3.3. GEOSS AND THE OCEAN.....	7
3.4. THE GEOSS PLATFORM.....	7
4. STAKEHOLDER DISCUSSIONS AND SELECTION PROCESS	9
4.1. BACKGROUND.....	9
4.2. STAKEHOLDER DISCUSSIONS	10
4.3. ALL ATLANTIC DATA PORTAL REQUIREMENTS	11
4.3.1. GENERAL REQUIREMENTS	11
4.3.2. SPECIFIC ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS	13
5. THE ALL ATLANTIC COMMUNITY PORTAL	13
5.1. INITIAL CATALOGUE.....	13
5.2. DATA DISCOVERY WITH CUSTOM FILTERS	14
6. FUTURE STEPS.....	14
Document Information	16

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The four components of the GEOSS platform.....	8
Figure 2: The recent developments of the GEOSS platform include new features, i.e. the GEOSS View, the GEOSS Mirror and the GEOSS Widget.	9
Figure 3: Two-step supported workflow for the registration of resources for new data providers.....	13
Figure 4: Gantt chart presenting the timeline for the launch and support of the GEOSS Portal throughout the lifetime of the iAtlantic Project.	15

1. SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on activities leading to the launch of an Atlantic Community portal in the GEOSS (Global Earth Observation System of Systems) Platform. It aims to draw together the international Atlantic observation community by strengthening and growing the network of actors in Atlantic Ocean observations. A functional interface will be built through a GEOSS portal community site. This new feature of the GEOSS portal allows users and data providers to build customisable sites around specific communities of interest. Data repositories in iAtlantic e.g. PANGAEA, NRF-SAEON (National Research Foundation – South African Environmental Observation Network) and EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network) will register relevant data through the portal and actively seek out additional contributors from other Atlantic Flagship projects (BG08 call), other Atlantic research initiatives, research infrastructures and industry. Work Package (WP) 7 partners will populate the site with relevant actors and data providers, including a catalogue of resources in GEOSS. The community pages will build on existing initiatives such as EMODnet. Particular attention will be paid to ensure complementarity between the GEOSS Community portal and the EMODnet. The focus will also include providing a forum for a community of practice and the need to increase our understanding of Essential Ocean Variables (e.g., dissolved organic carbon, particulate matter, and nutrients) for pelagic and deep-sea environments. Furthermore, the iAtlantic Associate Partner MBON (Marine Biodiversity Observation Network) will i) advice on the requirements for both observations & data working closely with iAtlantic beneficiaries and ii) work with iAtlantic to facilitate active linkages between iAtlantic, MBON and Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). ESA (European Space Agency) supports these efforts and will help with aspects of repository and data registration (e.g. by SAEON, South African Environment Observation Network) to make the site operational.

2. MOTIVATION FOR AN ALL ATLANTIC COMMUNITY DATA PORTAL

While there are a large number of distributed and sophisticated platforms to access marine data, few platforms exist where data can be accessed from a central point across disciplines and countries. As such, the GEOSS portal was created to provide this service to the international scientific community. Originally intended to visualize and share earth observation data from space, the portal now hosts data from many different observation infrastructures or research projects, and aims to be a one-stop shop for earth and environmental data.

From iAtlantic and the All Atlantic projects perspective it is critical to remember that there has been less ocean observation carried out in in the South Atlantic than the North Atlantic Ocean. In addition, South Atlantic datasets are often stored in local university archives or hard drives, making it extremely difficult to work collaboratively with researchers other relevant

stakeholders (e.g. policy makers). This situation is similar to that of the European Union before massive efforts to organise and fund national data archives were implemented (e.g. European efforts in form of the European Open Science Cloud and Blue Cloud in respect to marine data). Analogous efforts in the South Atlantic currently do not exist, even though the need for these essential infrastructures is widely accepted. To ensure that developments in the northern and southern hemisphere develop in unison, active collaborations and interactions are needed. The All Atlantic Community Site provides an opportunity to initiate enhanced exchange of knowledge, establish best practices, and align North and South Atlantic data management practices. Moreover, the All Atlantic Community Site will provide a collaborative space for the currently funded Atlantic research projects by helping make past and ongoing research data more easily discoverable.

3. GEOSS – THE GLOBAL EARTH OBSERVATION SYSTEM OF SYSTEMS

3.1. GEO – GROUP ON EARTH OBSERVATION

GEO (Group on Earth Observations; <https://earthobservations.org/index.php>) and GEOSS are closely linked entities. GEO is an intergovernmental organisation currently consisting of 105 national governments and more than 100 participating organisations who work with earth observations from a global perspective and for the societal benefit of all member and non-member states. The group connects many stakeholders including government institutions, academic and research institutions, data providers, businesses, engineers, scientists, and experts in order to create innovative solutions to global challenges at a time of exponential data growth, human development, and climate change that transcends national and disciplinary boundaries. GEO is a partnership which shares a common vision of advancing our knowledge and understanding of the earth system through access to global earth observations in a centralised, free, and open system. Furthermore, entities such as WMO (World Meteorological Organisation), WHO (World Health Organisation), UNESCO, the World Bank and POGO (Partnership for Observation of the Global Ocean) cooperate closely with GEO. A central and ongoing part of GEO's mission is to build GEOSS to ensure that global earth observations can be accessed and used by everyone.

GEOSS provides an overall framework for access to global earth observations for users, stakeholders, and decision makers. By offering services to make global earth observing systems' data and information freely discoverable and accessible through the GEOSS Platform (platform access at: <https://www.geoportal.org>), the benefit of these data for societies is maximised through provision of critical information about the global processes driving our earth system. In particular,

*“GEOSS is a set of coordinated, independent earth observation, information and processing systems that interact and provide access to diverse information for a broad range of users in both public and private sectors. **GEOSS links these systems to strengthen the monitoring of the state of the earth.** It facilitates the sharing of environmental data and information collected from the large array of observing systems contributed by countries and organizations within GEO. Further, GEOSS ensures that these data are accessible, of identified quality and provenance, and interoperable to support the development of tools and the delivery of information services. Thus, GEOSS increases our understanding of earth processes and enhances predictive capabilities that underpin sound decision-making: it provides access to data, information and knowledge to a wide variety of users.”¹*

While GEOSS’ focus is not on the collection of earth observation data per se, it acts as a centralised global access point to earth observation data available in other repositories and archives, research infrastructures, and academic institutions, etc. Registration of data resources by the original data providers with GEOSS can enable the discoverability of and access to relevant data through the GEOSS portal. This approach provides a central access point for users to existing earth observation data across geographical and political borders, scientific disciplines, and Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs). This provides better accessibility and discoverability of resources from earth observation programs and initiatives and further facilitates informed decision-making on a global scale, which is a prerequisite for dealing with global environmental challenges. In this way, GEOSS provides a comprehensive and sustainable single internet access point for earth observation data. Data resources discoverable through GEOSS amount to more than 400 million open data resources from more than 150 national and regional providers including: NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration GEO) and ESA, international organisations (e.g. WMO), the commercial sector (e.g. Digital Globe), in addition to research data archives such as SAEON and PANGAEA (Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science).

3.2. GEOSS – DATA AND RESOURCES

GEOSS was designed to make high quality data readily available in a timely and sustainable manner. Hence, GEOSS facilitates the swift transfer of data between the data provider and the user with minimal delay. GEOSS operates with a set of data sharing principles which ensure open and free access to the resources available. These principles have been implemented by GEO (Group on Earth Observations) and are required of all member states, who provide a letter endorsing the implementation plan for GEOSS, and thereby the GEOSS data sharing principles. The GEOSS data sharing principles are:

¹ <http://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

- a. There will be full and open exchange of data, metadata, and products shared within GEOSS, recognising relevant international instruments and national policies and legislation;
- b. All shared data, metadata, and products will be made available with minimum time delay and at minimum cost;
- c. All shared data, metadata, and products being free of charge or no more than the cost of production will be encouraged for research and education.²

From an Atlantic Ocean observation perspective it is important to note that these data sharing principles are in full agreement with the scope of the AtlantOS data management plan.³

3.3. GEOSS AND THE OCEAN

GEO and GEOSS are concerned with all kinds of environmental data, whether it be atmospheric, terrestrial, or aquatic. However, the strong role of the ocean on our earth system has led to a special focus on ocean observations and a need to extract information from the available data. The “Oceans and Society: Blue Planet” initiative within GEO aims to ensure sustained development and use of ocean and coastal observations for the benefit of society. Through the GEO Blue Planet initiative, GEO has generated an initiative with a specific focus on ocean observations, where GEO, in collaboration with various ocean data providers, facilitates coordination and capacity building initiatives for ocean observations. A network of scientists, marine observers, and user group representatives, (e.g. international organisations, NGOs, governments, and academic institutions) collaborate to bridge the gap between data and services and deliverable information needed to inform decision-making and meet sustainable development goals.

3.4. THE GEOSS PLATFORM

In 2017, the GEOSS Common Infrastructure (GCI) changed its name to the GEOSS Platform. Essential features of the platform are presented below (Figure 1) to support the later discussion about the suitability of the portal and its services to the iAtlantic objectives and the wider Atlantic Ocean research community. For a full overview and detailed descriptions, we refer to the GEOSS Platform Manual⁴, from where the information was derived.

The GEOSS Platform provides the technological tools to implement the Global Earth Observation System of Systems. The GEOSS Platform facilitates users to search, access and

² Text extracted from [the GEO Strategic Plan 2016-2025](#) (page 11)

³ AtlantOS Project Data Management Plan Framework
<http://oceanrep.geomar.de/39237/1/11.2%20Data%20Management%20Plan-1.pdf>

⁴ GEOSS Platform Manual V1, https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/gci/201711_gci_manual_01.pdf

use data, information, tools and other services from various providers around the world through the Global Earth Observation System of Systems.

Figure 1: The four components of the GEOSS platform

GEOSS - New features for communities

GEOSS is moving towards a more user-centric approach to data and resource sharing, which can better accommodate specific user communities and their needs in terms of specific interests (e.g. geographical or temporal), filtering options (displaying only selected data), and functionalities. In order to accommodate larger scientific communities, like the All Atlantic research community, recent developments of the GEOSS platform include new features (Figure 2), thus allowing communities to customise their entry to the GEOSS platform and thereby become discoverable (as communities), displaying their scopes as well as their data and other resources.

GEOSS View is a feature allowing communities to define and install data filters and display specifically defined resources relating to the communities' focus. The filtering and display of resources can also be used to ensure that data format and access follow certain criteria. This allows communities to generate a filtered display of resources (e.g. resources coming exclusively from the partners of these communities). Furthermore, it provides the opportunity to generate thematic and spatial filters, hence allowing communities to specifically target only their areas of interest (e.g. marine data from the Atlantic Ocean).

GEOSS Mirror is a GEOSS Portal site customisation for communities as well as SBAs, flagships, and initiatives. It allows the community to configure a community customised entry point through the GEOSS Portal (e.g. www.geoPortal.org/community/<NameOfTheCommunity>). The customisation allows for the display of specific text relevant to the community, as well as text as usage of 'Views' (see GEOSS View) to filter and display resources relevant to the community.

GEOSS Widget allows communities to generate widgets (embedded applications) to display essential resources. This is accomplished by publishing portal code parts (widgets) wrapped up in APIs which plug into the portal site. In the case of iAtlantic, the GeoNode could potentially embed APIs that allow data visualisations for specific data sets.

Figure 2: The recent developments of the GEOSS platform include new features, i.e. the GEOSS View, the GEOSS Mirror and the GEOSS Widget.

4. STAKEHOLDER DISCUSSIONS AND SELECTION PROCESS

4.1. BACKGROUND

Many projects and initiatives, which produce or use large amounts of data, create their own data portals to integrate or pool their resources with those from other sources and make it available to other researchers. While this may be suitable for long-term funded initiatives, most efforts from time-limited projects lose their supporting resources with the termination of the project funding. Nevertheless, iAtlantic partners on WP7 actively engage in leveraging the data resources generated by past and present Atlantic research projects and other initiatives, to create visibility and enhanced impact of the data resources. Another driving force behind these plans is to help align the availability of marine research data across the North and South Atlantic. Over the last decade, many European countries have made great progress in the management of their research data through improved archiving, curation, common standards, licensing, and provenance, etc. Indeed, the European Commission took a leading role in coordinating, enforcing, and financing many of these developments, which cumulated in rapidly maturing data landscapes with overarching infrastructures across Europe (e.g. EMODNet, SeaDataNet, EOSC, BlueCloud). While the National Science Foundation fulfilled this role in the USA, many South American and African countries have not established mature and long-term sustainable data infrastructures with trained personnel. There is a need

for a culture change that will promote the sharing, reuse of research data for open, transparent, and accountable science, and maximise research investments in many other parts around the Atlantic. By establishing a GEOSS Community portal for the Atlantic Ocean research community and actively engaging South Atlantic partners, iAtlantic will pursue several overarching objectives:

- a. Increase the visibility and impact of research data available for the Atlantic Ocean basin from past and current research by providing a central access point through the GEOSS portal. iAtlantic will build on the very large group of international data providers already registered with GEOSS.
- b. Actively encourage South Atlantic data infrastructures to share data (or metadata) through the GEOSS Community site. By increasing the data visibility and use (also through showcasing the fruits of such collaboration), iAtlantic hopes that political leverage for investments in these infrastructures can be generated on local and/or national levels.
- c. Following the directives of the Belem statements and the supporting AANChOR (All Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and Innovation) and AtlantOS initiatives, iAtlantic plans to establish a means to bring the Atlantic research community together and facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices. The portal will also support the AANChOR goal to establish an All Atlantic Data Portal (AANChOR WP5).

4.2. STAKEHOLDER DISCUSSIONS

Buy-in from other EU projects is essential for the success of the site. As such, initial informal discussions were held in 2020 at the AANChOR workshop in Brussels, and again during the following All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum. These meetings also provided opportunities to engage with South African and Brazilian ministerial representatives who provided very positive feedback. Furthermore, iAtlantic WP7 partners (i.e., UniHB, EMODnet and SAEON) scheduled direct meetings with stakeholders (i.e., TRIATLAS, AtlantECO, Mission Atlantic, ASTRAL, AtlantOS, AANChOR and international partners) to introduce the GEOSS portal (by Guido Colangeli, ESA), discuss our concept for the community site and collect feedback ([Table 1](#)).

Table 1: Meetings to introduce the GEOSS Portal, discuss its concept and engage with stakeholders.

Meeting	Date/Place	Participants
AANChOR workshop on Ocean Data Management	5 th February 2020, Brussels	'Ocean Experts' (i.e., researchers, data experts, people working in ministries & AANChOR partners) from around the Atlantic: all four continents bordering the Atlantic were represented
All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum	6 th – 7 th February 2020, Brussels	Networking with other projects (e.g., ASTRAL, Mission Atlantic, AtlantECO, AtlantOS, Blue Cloud) & international forum participants
Introduction to the GEOSS Portal meeting	February 2020, Online	Coordinators/data managers from TRIATLAS, Summer, AtlantOS, AtlantECO, Mission Atlantic, AANChOR, SAEON, Claudia Alves de Magalhães from the Brazilian Ministry of Science & Technology

Concrete plans for the implementation of the portal were also embedded by iAtlantic in the AANChOR WP5 joint action proposal (AANCHOR D5.4 – Proposed Joint Actions Addressing Common Standards for Information and Data Sharing), which was recently approved for funding. The Joint Action will help the site align with the Blue Cloud and EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) data standards (where possible) and work towards enhanced interoperability with new data providers. Other networks (e.g. EUROMARINE) and project interactions were used to generate interest and feedback for the site plans by all iAtlantic WP7 partners. Further meetings in late 2020 were planned with Brad de Young (AtlantOS) for All Atlantic Stakeholder discussions. However, these meeting were cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic travel restrictions and have not been rescheduled yet. Formal and informal networking is essential for this type of activity, which has suffered considerably from the lack of opportunities to speak to stakeholders at key meetings. Project participants were also considered 'users', as they are part of the Atlantic Ocean research community, and were encouraged to provide feedback on desired functionalities of the site and definitions of added value for their projects or areas of research.

4.3. ALL ATLANTIC DATA PORTAL REQUIREMENTS

4.3.1. GENERAL REQUIREMENTS

Essential features of the portal's supporting infrastructure were identified during stakeholder meetings prior to detailing the requirements of the community site. While the GEOSS platform was identified by the iAtlantic project as suitable, iAtlantic initiated a discussion regarding other options. Several key factors were identified to gauge the suitability of the

GEOSS (or other suggested) platform to host the portal.

- a. The portal's infrastructure should not be 'European', but with an international profile to attract an international user and data provider pool, without creating national or regional inhibitions. In addition, the portal should avoid branding by any individual project or regional/national initiative.
- b. The portal's underlying infrastructure should already be established, known in the community, and long-term sustainable in its own right. The portal, once established, should remain functional and technically maintained by the supporting infrastructure and staff. This will ensure that the portal is not dependent on project duration or 'continuation' of funding.
- c. Considering that there may be large differences in the maturity of data infrastructures wanting to connect their resources through the portal, the portal framework needs to allow for variability in maturity. However, the advantages of detailed metadata records and high data archiving standards should also be exploitable by the community.
- d. The portal needs to fulfil user requirements in respect to functionalities of the site and data content.

The requirements were developed by iAtlantic's WP7 partners during the first discussions with stakeholders and through helpful discussions with Brad de Young (AtlantOS). The GEOSS infrastructure was measured against these requirements for suitability and evaluated for potential weaknesses. The GEOSS platform fulfils the requirements a-c mentioned above (requirement d depends on the features implemented in the Community Site and current developments in GEOSS) and was therefore selected to host the community site. The GEOSS infrastructure has several weak points, which iAtlantic plans to address:

1. The platform can be unstable, but bug fixing and maintenance is commissioned to the ESA. However, reporting of these issues is left to the community (or any user of the site).
2. It is unclear how many features can be implemented overall. In the most basic version of the Community site, iAtlantic would still be able to establish a data portal with a searchable metadata catalogue, providing direct access to Atlantic data whenever the data providers enable this (i.e., no separate log in on data provider side or need to send data requests). Filtering during data searches would mirror the GEOSS Portal mechanisms, but could be improved with additional parameters.

Additional benefits of the GEOSS platform not listed in the requirements are the well-

established protocols and workflows to help data providers register their data. After an initial effort is made by data providers to register through the ‘yellow pages’, data providers receive individual support until the registration is completed. If approved by the data provider, new metadata and data links are harvested at regular intervals so that the full catalogue is available without further effort (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Two-step supported workflow for the registration of resources for new data providers.

4.3.2. SPECIFIC ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS

While the GEOSS portal is fit to discover data set metadata and access individual data sets, it currently lacks the functionality to discover, aggregate, and bulk-access data from different sources at the granularity of observations. A bulk download from diverse sources after the discovery phase is currently being developed, but has not been fully implemented yet. In addition, the data provided through GEOSS is often capable of providing the expected granularity (e.g. OBIS, Ocean Biodiversity Information System, and GBIF, Global Biodiversity Information Facility). iAtlantic will therefore work with GEOSS to explore technical solutions to satisfy this requirement, whenever the data in the underlying data archive is structured in such a way to allow this granularity.

5. THE ALL ATLANTIC COMMUNITY PORTAL

5.1. INITIAL CATALOGUE

To initiate the launch of the portal, iAtlantic has focused on selecting a subset of Atlantic data resources from the main portal coming from trusted data sources. In addition, PANGAEA and SAEON, as well as past and current Atlantic projects (e.g., ATLAS, TRIATLAS, AtlantOS) will filter their data resources. To complete the initial catalogue for the prototype portal, iAtlantic

Deliverable D5.2 'Atlantic Regions of Interest' and AANChOR Deliverable 'Baseline Initiatives' will serve as additional resources to identify useful data sources and complete the initial catalogue.

Effort will be made to include large datasets of previously aggregated data (e.g. SeaDataNet, Argo floats data). Many of the resources listed in the GEOSS Portal cannot be directly accessed due to additional log in requirements at the level of the data provider. Therefore, iAtlantic will focus more on resources in the GEOSS Core (direct access and download), rather than sending users to external sources during their data discovery phase. The initial catalogue will serve primarily to support iAtlantic efforts to encourage South Atlantic partners on any of the BG08 Projects to engage with GEOSS and explore options for data sharing through the portal or another archive, or define additional needs to enable that development. In order to encourage community participation in the site, iAtlantic will encourage suggestions for data to include in the catalogue.

5.2. DATA DISCOVERY WITH CUSTOM FILTERS

The process of filtering data during data discovery is crucial, as it will determine the discoverability and the reuse impact of the data. There are many data portals for marine data, GEOSS, however, is unique in its interdisciplinary character and international scope. Nevertheless, the sheer mass of data is difficult to sift through and can reduce the overall experience and success. Therefore, iAtlantic will successively develop filters to optimise data discovery, while also including filters to reflect the community participants (i.e. projects or communities within the marine community). Moreover, iAtlantic will encourage other marine communities (e.g. HABs community, Sargasso Sea, Marine Plastics) to make their catalogue accessible through the portal as well. Filters will again help to reduce the noise.

6. FUTURE STEPS

iAtlantic aims to extend our initial catalogue during the lifetime of the project to include newly generated data (Figure 4). It is also envisioned that the site will be useful for generating collaborative ideas between different projects, initiatives, and local players. Providing a simple entry point for new data providers can help identify local and regional data management needs and possibly provide some political leverage. Following discussions and plans with the AANChOR project, we hope that the GEOSS All Atlantic Community site may grow into an All Atlantic Open Data Space with a wide participation from the different North and South Atlantic stakeholders.

Figure 4: Gantt chart presenting the timeline for the launch and support of the GEOSS Portal throughout the lifetime of the iAtlantic Project.

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